

**OPEN EDUCATIONAL
RESOURCES TO ADVANCE
FAIR DATA STEWARDSHIP
IN LIFE SCIENCES & HEALTH**

INTRODUCING THE
LEARNFAIR PROJECT

Funded by

LEARNFAIR

Why LEARNFAIR?

Findable, Accessible,
Interoperable, and Reusable

Researchers and support staff are increasingly **required to make data FAIR**

They need **accessible, high-quality training** to effectively do so

FAIR training materials are **fragmented, inaccessible, and often not FAIR** themselves

Trainers can benefit from aligned efforts to **share and improve resources**

Aims

to foster collaboration, share resources,
and connect stakeholders

Establish **a community of FAIR trainers** from research performing and supporting organizations

Develop a community-adopted set of **open educational resources** on FAIR Data Stewardship

ready-to-use and openly
available lesson plans, curricula,
and training materials

Work packages

Community building,
engagement
& dissemination

Development
of a federated
infrastructure

Development
of educational
materials

Identification of
existing resources
& learning needs

Partners

Amsterdam UMC

Leiden University
Medical Center

health RI

enabling data driven health & life sciences

Maastricht University

Radboudumc

university medical center

Want to learn ~~FAIR~~ more?

[LEARNFAIR.nl](https://learnfair.nl)